

Legal basis for strengthening democratic principles in parliamentary activity

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Abstract

The legal basis for strengthening democratic principles in the activities of the Parliament of the Republic of Uzbekistan is analyzed. It is substantiated that the Parliament is the highest representative body ensuring democratic governance as a practical expression of people's sovereignty. The study covers constitutional and regulatory mechanisms, in particular, the principles of freedom of elections, multi-party system, openness, responsibility of deputies and parliamentary control. Based on legal analysis, comparative and systematic approaches, the experience of Uzbekistan is compared with foreign parliamentary practice. As a result, it was determined that further strengthening democratic principles in parliamentary activities will serve to ensure transparency, balance and participation of civil society in state governance.

Keywords: Parliament, democracy, legal basis, freedom of elections, multi-party system, openness, parliamentary control, constitution, people's sovereignty, civil society.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the process of forming a democratic legal state and civil society has become a pressing issue worldwide. At the center of this process is the parliamentary institution, which is the most important expression of the idea of people's power. Parliament acts as a central structure that ensures a balance between political forces in society, expresses the will of the people in the form of law, and determines the democratic mechanism of state power. In the historical development of democratic states, the role of parliaments has been diverse, but they all have a common feature - enacting laws on behalf of the people and exercising control over the government. In this sense, parliament is not only a body that develops laws, but also an important guarantee of the stability, openness and dialogue with the people of the political system. After the Republic of Uzbekistan gained independence, the national state governance system was formed based on democratic values. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, adopted in 1992, determined the legal basis for the division of branches of power in the country and the activities of representative bodies. On this basis, the Oliy

Majlis was established in 1995 and began to function as the highest representative body of state power. Later, the transition to a bicameral parliamentary system in 2005 served to further implement democratic principles.

The parliament of the Republic of Uzbekistan consists of the Legislative Chamber and the Senate, the powers, structure and principles of their activities are determined by the Law “On the Oliy Majlis”. These legal frameworks allow for the democratic organization of parliamentary activities, ensuring a real mechanism of people's representation and exercising parliamentary control over the government. Democratic principles are the foundation of parliamentary activities. Among them, such principles as people's sovereignty, freedom of elections, multi-party system, openness and transparency, independence of deputies, parliamentary control, and participation of civil society occupy a special place. Therefore, strengthening these principles legally and providing them with mechanisms that work effectively in practice is an important direction of modern reforms. In recent years, within the framework of the “New Uzbekistan” concept, democratic reforms have been deepening in Uzbekistan, and new mechanisms are being formed, such as increasing the openness of parliamentary activities, expanding the participation of civil society in lawmaking, and introducing an electronic parliament system. This process is aimed at transforming parliamentary activities into a more people-oriented, accountable, and effective system.

First of all, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the main source that strengthens democratic principles in parliamentary activities. Article 7 of the Constitution states that “The people are the only source of state power,” and this norm ensures that the parliament acts on behalf of the people. Articles 76–89 also legally define the structure, powers, procedure for enacting laws, and inter-chamber relations of the Oliy Majlis.

The principle of freedom of elections is the main guarantee of the democratic functioning of the parliament. The Law “On Elections to the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan” grants every citizen the right to vote and be elected, which is a practical manifestation of people's sovereignty. The conduct of elections on the basis of transparency, equality, and competitiveness forms a democratic parliamentary system.

The multi-party system is also an important component of the democratic environment in the parliament. The Law “On Political Parties” creates equal conditions for political competition, as a result of which different political views are embodied in

the parliament. This ensures balance in decision-making and reflects the harmony of social interests.

The institution of parliamentary oversight is also legally based as an integral element of democratic governance. In accordance with the Law “On Parliamentary Oversight”, the Oliy Majlis analyzes the activities of the government, considers the execution of the state budget, and hears reports from the Prime Minister. This strengthens the accountability of the executive branch to the parliament. Documents such as the Regulations “On the Chambers of the Supreme Council”, the Law “On the Status of a Deputy”, and the Law “On Regulatory and Legal Acts” ensure the independence of deputies, the openness of the law-making process, and the transparency of legal processes. Within the framework of the “New Uzbekistan” strategy, the legal framework for parliamentary activities has been further improved. In particular, mechanisms such as submitting draft laws to public discussion, holding open hearings, introducing an electronic parliament system, and expanding the participation of civil society institutions have been legally strengthened.

Conclusion

Strengthening democratic principles in parliamentary activities is a key condition for building a legal state. A constitutional and legislative framework has been created in this direction in the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the principles of people's sovereignty, freedom of elections, multi-party system, openness, and parliamentary oversight are being strengthened in practice. At the same time, expanding openness in parliamentary activities, increasing the accountability of deputies, and strengthening the participation of civil society remain important areas of democratic reform.

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